

GENDER AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT: ATTITUDES OF MOROCCAN EFL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This article explores how gender shapes Moroccan EFL (English as a Foreign Language) teachers' attitudes toward professional development (PD). Drawing on a mixed-methods design, it combines data from an online survey of 87 teachers across Moroccan regions with qualitative insights from eight semi-structured interviews. The study examines general attitudes, perceived barriers, and gender-related dimensions of collaboration and leadership in PD. While statistical analysis revealed no significant gender-based differences overall, qualitative findings suggest female teachers experience unique socio-cultural pressures that subtly affect their engagement, leadership roles, and collaborative practices. Bourdieu's concept of *habitus* and Hofer & Lembens' model of teacher attitudes provide the theoretical underpinning. The findings raise critical questions about the inclusiveness of PD frameworks and the need for gender-sensitive planning in Morocco's education reform. Recommendations are made for policymakers, teacher educators, and PD program designers.

Keywords: Gender, habitus, teacher collaboration, teacher professional development.

1. Introduction

Efforts to improve educational systems worldwide, including in Morocco, have consistently emphasized the importance of high-quality teaching. Foundational policy documents such as Morocco's *National Charter for Education and Training* (1999), the *Emergency Plan* (2009), and the *Strategic Vision 2015–2030* highlight the centrality of teacher effectiveness in achieving meaningful reform. These initiatives mirror global policy trends seen in programs like the United States' *No Child Left Behind Act* and the OECD's international

education strategies, all of which converge on the notion that teachers are among the most influential factors affecting student achievement (Fullan & Miles, 1992; Hanushek, 1992; Chetty et al., 2014).

According to Hanushek (1992), the difference between an effective and ineffective teacher can amount to a full academic year's worth of learning gains. Consequently, improving teacher capacity through continuous professional development (PD) has become a cornerstone of education reform across systems. PD is no longer viewed as a supplementary activity but as a lifelong necessity that supports teachers in keeping up with evolving pedagogies, curricula, and student needs.

Morocco's *Strategic Vision for Education 2015–2030* articulates this clearly, calling on policymakers to diversify the forms of continuous teacher training and to institutionalize PD across the entirety of a teacher's career. Despite these ambitions, PD is often conceptualized and implemented as a one-size-fits-all strategy, overlooking contextual and demographic factors such as gender. This oversight assumes a level playing field, where all teachers—regardless of gender, region, or personal circumstances—engage with and benefit from PD in equal measure.

However, teaching, like any other profession, is embedded in broader social, cultural, and institutional structures. Teachers enter the profession with personal histories, beliefs, and identities that shape their perceptions and engagement. Gender, in particular, plays a significant role in professional identity formation. Social expectations, familial responsibilities, and institutional cultures can all interact with gender to influence how teachers experience and value professional development.

In the Moroccan context, the influence of gender in educational decision-making and institutional structures remains underexplored, especially in the realm of in-service teacher development. While national strategies advocate for equity and inclusiveness, they fall short of explicitly addressing gender-sensitive planning in PD. This gap raises important questions: Do male and female teachers perceive PD opportunities and challenges differently? Are there structural or social factors that limit one group's engagement more than the other? And does gender affect the dynamics of collaboration and leadership within PD settings?

This study emerges from such questions. As an ELT supervisor and former classroom teacher, the researcher observed first-hand the unequal participation of male and female teachers in PD activities. These observations led to the hypothesis that gender may influence not only access to but also attitudes towards professional development. To test this, the study

investigates EFL teachers' perceptions of PD with a particular focus on gender as a possible shaping factor.

Grounded in both quantitative and qualitative methodologies, the research combines a national online survey with in-depth interviews. Bourdieu's sociological theory, particularly his concept of *habitus*, provides the analytical lens to interpret how social structures, especially gender, manifest in individual and group behavior. The work also draws on contemporary models of teacher learning that stress the importance of context, collaboration, and personal meaning-making in shaping PD engagement (Hofer & Lembens, 2019).

The central aim of this study is to determine whether male and female EFL teachers in Morocco exhibit different attitudes toward PD and whether such differences are statistically significant or primarily shaped by subjective and contextual experiences. The research also explores the broader implications of these findings for PD planning and gender equity in education reform.

This article argues that while statistical data may show no strong gender-based differentiation in general PD attitudes, qualitative insights reveal nuanced socio-cultural dynamics that disproportionately affect female teachers' leadership roles and participation in collaborative PD. These insights point to the need for more gender-responsive PD planning in Morocco and beyond.

2. Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1. Understanding Professional Development and Teacher Attitudes

Professional development (PD) is widely recognized as a fundamental element in educational improvement. It encompasses a broad range of activities that enable teachers to enhance their knowledge, skills, and practices beyond their initial training (Craft, 1996). Contemporary perspectives emphasize PD as a dynamic, collaborative, and reflective process rather than a top-down transmission of knowledge (Diaz-Maggioli, 2004; Guskey, 1995).

Teacher engagement in PD is deeply influenced by individual attitudes—understood as predispositions to respond positively or negatively to certain stimuli, practices, or experiences (Simpson et al., 1996). Attitudes are shaped by beliefs, personal and professional experiences, and emotional responses. They influence how teachers interpret their roles, relate to colleagues, and approach learning opportunities (Jones & Carter, 2007). Thus, investigating teachers' attitudes toward PD is essential for understanding both participation and effectiveness.

Hofer and Lembens (2019) present a model in which teacher attitudes are formed by the interaction of three components: knowledge and skills, beliefs, and affective factors. These are embedded in sociocultural contexts that shape both teachers' self-perception and their professional behavior. The model highlights the recursive relationship between attitudes and practice, attitudes inform professional behavior, which in turn reinforces or reshapes attitudes.

2.2. The Gender Dimension in Professional Life

Gender has long been recognized as a social and cultural construct that influences individuals' roles and opportunities in both public and private spheres (Cranny-Francis et al., 2003). Within educational institutions, gendered expectations often manifest in the form of unequal leadership opportunities, differential treatment, and varying levels of comfort or authority in professional spaces.

Early sociological theories, such as those of Comte and Durkheim, reinforced essentialist views of gender by suggesting biological determinism. However, contemporary scholarship, particularly feminist and post-structuralist theories, has challenged these views, highlighting how gender is produced and reproduced through discourse, social norms, and institutional practices (Friedan, 1963; Foucault, 1978; Bohan, 1993). Schools, as microcosms of society, often mirror the gender dynamics found in broader social contexts.

In the context of professional development, gender can influence access, participation, collaboration, and leadership. For example, some studies suggest that female teachers may experience barriers such as time constraints due to family responsibilities, lower self-efficacy in leadership roles, or discomfort in male-dominated professional spaces (Çiğdem Hürsen, 2012; Badri et al., 2016). Other studies, however, report no significant gender-based differences in PD engagement or attitudes (Lessing & de Witt, 2007; Huang & Shih, 2017).

This inconsistency in findings suggests that context matters. Cultural norms, institutional practices, and socio-economic factors intersect with gender in complex ways. In Morocco, despite progressive reform discourses, gender-sensitive frameworks are largely absent in PD planning and teacher training. The lack of localized research on gender and PD further obscures the issue.

2.3. Bourdieu's Sociological Theory and the Concept of Habitus

To make sense of the interplay between social structures and individual attitudes, this study employs Pierre Bourdieu's concept of *habitus* (Bourdieu, 1977; 1990). Habitus refers to the internalized system of dispositions through which individuals perceive and react to the social world. It encompasses not only learned behaviors but also unconscious attitudes, intuitions, and tastes, shaped by historical and social conditions.

According to Bourdieu, individuals operate within *fields*, social spaces such as education, religion, or art, where power is negotiated and distributed. Each field has its own rules, expectations, and capital (economic, cultural, or symbolic). The teaching profession is one such field, and PD activities represent structured spaces within it.

When applied to gender, Bourdieu's theory helps explain how male and female teachers might experience PD differently, even if they hold similar positions. *Gendered habitus* refers to the way in which cultural norms about femininity and masculinity are internalized and expressed in behavior. These internalized norms influence what roles teachers feel comfortable assuming, how they interact with colleagues, and how they perceive opportunities for growth.

Bourdieu also introduces the concept of *symbolic violence*, the subtle, often invisible ways in which dominant social norms perpetuate inequality. In professional development contexts, symbolic violence may occur when PD events are scheduled without regard for teachers' caregiving responsibilities, when female teachers feel marginalized in collaborative spaces, or when leadership roles are unofficially reserved for men.

2.4. International and Regional Studies on Gender and PD

Several international studies have explored gender differences in PD, with mixed findings. In the UK, Hustler et al. (2003) found no significant gender effects in teacher perceptions of PD. Similarly, Huang and Shih (2017) in Taiwan reported no meaningful gender differences among primary school teachers. Yates (2007) and Lessing and de Witt (2007) reached similar conclusions.

However, other studies suggest that gender-related experiences do influence PD engagement. Taşdemir (2013) found that female teachers in Turkey were more likely to express interest in PD but were less likely to participate due to familial constraints. Çiğdem Hürsen (2012) discovered that female teachers in Northern Cyprus showed more positive attitudes toward PD than their male counterparts. The OECD's *Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS)* (2018) also found that while gender alone was not a major factor, it intersected with motivations, values, and work-life balance.

In the Arab world, Badri et al. (2016) found that male and female teachers in Abu Dhabi had differing perceptions of their PD needs. Female teachers expressed greater needs for ICT training, while male teachers emphasized administrative leadership. This suggests that even when access is equal, the perceived value and focus of PD may differ by gender.

In Morocco, empirical research on this issue remains limited. Ziad (2016) studied Moroccan teachers' attitudes towards ICT integration and found no significant gender-based differences, but the scope of the study did not extend to general PD attitudes. This gap in the literature highlights the need for localized, context-sensitive investigations such as the present study.

2.5. The Need for Gender-Sensitive PD Planning

Despite the diversity of perspectives, one theme remains consistent: effective PD must be responsive to teachers' realities. This includes recognizing and addressing how gendered expectations, both institutional and cultural, shape teachers' experiences. Professional development that ignores these dimensions risks alienating or under-serving parts of the teaching workforce, thereby undermining both equity and effectiveness.

Bourdieu's theoretical lens offers a way to move beyond surface-level differences and examine how seemingly neutral practices reinforce systemic inequalities. When PD structures are designed without accounting for gendered roles or constraints, they may reproduce a field in which male teachers thrive while female teachers must navigate additional barriers. Therefore, a gender-sensitive approach does not imply preferential treatment; rather, it aims to ensure equity of access, relevance, and participation.

3. Methodology

This study adopts a convergent parallel mixed-methods design to explore Moroccan EFL teachers' attitudes toward professional development, with gender as a key variable. The decision to integrate both quantitative and qualitative data stems from the belief that a more comprehensive understanding of attitudes can be reached when numerical patterns are complemented by personal insights and lived experiences.

3.1. Research Questions and Hypothesis

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What general attitudes do Moroccan male and female EFL teachers hold towards professional development?
2. Are there statistically significant differences between these attitudes?
3. How does gender influence professional collaboration and leadership in PD activities?

Based on preliminary observations and the theoretical framework, the study formulated the following hypothesis:

H1: Gender has a significant impact on Moroccan EFL teachers' attitudes toward professional development.

3.2. Participants

Survey Participants

The quantitative phase of the study included 87 EFL teachers from all 12 regional education academies in Morocco. Gender representation was approximately 62.1% male and 37.9% female. Teachers ranged in age from early-career professionals in their mid-20s to veterans in their late 40s and beyond.

To ensure regional diversity, participants were selected using stratified random sampling, with approximately eight participants per region, except for Dakhla Oued Dahab and L'Oriental, which had fewer available respondents.

Interview Participants

The qualitative component consisted of eight semi-structured interviews with four male and four female EFL teachers. Participants were chosen using purposive sampling to represent a diversity of regions, teaching levels, marital statuses, and years of experience. Interviews were conducted online due to COVID-19 restrictions.

3.3. Data Collection Instruments

Online Survey

The primary data collection tool for the quantitative phase was a Google Forms questionnaire, which was piloted with 12 teachers to ensure clarity, usability, and reliability. The survey included:

- **Demographic questions** (age, gender, marital status, region, level taught)
- **Likert-scale items** measuring general PD attitudes
- **Items on collaboration, satisfaction, leadership, and gendered perspectives**

The final dataset included complete responses from all 87 participants.

Semi-Structured Interviews

The interview guide was developed based on themes that emerged from the survey pilot and the literature review. Questions focused on:

- Perceptions of PD opportunities and leadership
- Gender-related collaboration dynamics
- Personal experiences navigating PD as a male or female teacher

Interviews lasted between 20–30 minutes, were conducted via video conferencing tools, and were recorded with participant consent.

3.4. Data Analysis

Quantitative Analysis

Survey data was exported to Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize general attitudes. Chi-square tests were employed to examine potential associations between gender and specific PD-related variables, such as satisfaction, collaboration, and leadership participation.

Where appropriate, cross-tabulations were used to explore intersections between gender and other variables like family status and level of teaching.

Qualitative Analysis

Interview transcripts were analyzed thematically using a coding framework grounded in both the research questions and emergent themes. Codes were grouped under broader categories, such as:

- Collaboration and communication across genders
- Comfort with leadership roles
- Impact of social norms and family responsibilities

Care was taken to compare and contrast male and female perspectives while maintaining the individual voice of each participant.

3.5. Ethical Considerations

All participants were informed about the nature of the study, the confidentiality of their responses, and their right to withdraw at any time. Data was anonymized to protect participants' identities. The study followed standard ethical procedures aligned with academic research practices in Moroccan higher education institutions.

3.6. Limitations of the Methodology

While the mixed-methods approach offers a rich understanding of gender and PD, the sample size limits generalizability. Additionally, the use of online tools (due to pandemic restrictions) may have excluded some teachers less comfortable with digital platforms. Nonetheless, the sample included participants from a broad range of regions and backgrounds, increasing its representativeness.

4. Findings

This section presents the results of both the quantitative survey and the qualitative interviews. Findings are organized into five thematic areas: (1) general attitudes toward professional development, (2) perceptions of PD practices, (3) gender-related experiences, (4) socio-cultural influences, and (5) interview-based insights into collaboration and gender dynamics.

4.1. General Attitudes Toward Professional Development

The survey revealed overwhelmingly positive attitudes toward PD among both male and female teachers:

- 79.3% of participants strongly agreed that PD is an "absolute necessity."
- 82.8% strongly agreed that PD is a "lifelong commitment."
- 100% agreed (strongly or partly) that teachers are personally responsible for their professional development.

These results indicate a broad consensus on the value and importance of PD, regardless of gender. Teachers showed awareness of modern conceptions of teacher learning as continuous, reflective, and self-directed.

4.2. Attitudes Toward PD Practices and Implementation

Supervisor Visits and Pedagogical Meetings

- Over 81% of respondents found supervisor/mentor classroom visits either "beneficial" or "very beneficial."
- A similar percentage expressed positive views of pedagogical meetings with supervisors.

Collaboration With Colleagues

- Teachers reported highly favorable attitudes toward peer collaboration, with more than 90% rating it as beneficial.
- Professional associations such as MATE (Moroccan Association of Teachers of English) were viewed positively, with most participants having attended or expressed interest in their PD events.

Trainer Responsiveness and Inclusiveness

When asked whether trainers or supervisors were mindful of participants' circumstances, only about 40% said "always." Others reported less consistency, with many stating only "occasionally" or "rarely."

Regarding inclusiveness and democracy in PD meeting management, roughly 75% of respondents believed meetings were often or always inclusive. However, a significant minority expressed concerns about favoritism, poor representation, or a lack of open dialogue.

4.3. Personal Satisfaction and Relevance of PD

Respondents were asked if PD activities in their region met their professional needs:

- Only 42.5% said the activities "always" met their needs.
- 35.6% responded "often," while others selected "occasionally" or "rarely."

A Chi-square test was conducted to determine if there was a statistically significant relationship between gender and satisfaction with PD:

- $p = 0.548$, which indicates **no significant gender-based difference** in levels of satisfaction.
Nevertheless, some patterns were observed:
- **Female teachers were slightly more likely** to report that PD activities "rarely" or "occasionally" met their needs.
- Males were somewhat more represented in the "always" and "often" satisfaction categories.

4.4. Gender-Specific Challenges and Perceptions

The survey included targeted questions about gender and its impact on PD participation.

Family Responsibilities

A majority of participants agreed or partly agreed that teachers with family responsibilities (especially women) tend to be less involved in PD. Respondents attributed this to time constraints, travel challenges, and lack of institutional support for caregivers.

Leadership Roles

When asked whether female teachers find it harder to take leadership roles in PD activities:

- A significant majority agreed or strongly agreed.
- Only a small minority strongly disagreed.

Use of Technology in PD

There was no significant gender difference in managing WhatsApp or other professional social media groups for EFL teaching. This suggests that digital spaces offer more equitable opportunities for engagement than traditional in-person PD structures.

4.5. Statistical Summary of Gender and PD Attitudes

The study conducted multiple Chi-square analyses to test the impact of gender on:

- General attitudes toward PD
- Satisfaction with PD activities
- Views on gender in PD planning and leadership
- Perceptions of collaboration

In all cases, no statistically significant difference was found between male and female responses.

For example, on the question “Does teacher gender impact PD engagement?” the p-value was 0.628, well above the threshold for significance. A similar result was observed when testing the relationship between gender, family status, and satisfaction ($p = 0.364$). While quantitative data suggests parity in attitude, qualitative data tells a more nuanced story.

4.6. Interview Insights: Gender and Professional Collaboration

The interviews revealed that while male teachers generally rejected the idea that gender impacts collaboration, many female teachers disagreed.

Some illustrative responses from female teachers:

“We live in a society that places more restrictions on women. I don’t feel free to collaborate openly with male colleagues.”

— Female teacher, Essmara, 26, single

“I prefer to work with other women. It’s not about capacity, it’s about comfort and social expectations.”

— Female teacher, Laayoune, 39, married with 4 children

“There’s very little communication between male and female teachers in my school. That limits co-teaching and collaboration.”

— Female teacher, Casablanca, 29, single

Interestingly, some female teachers proposed online collaboration as a way to overcome discomfort and traditional boundaries. This was seen as a “disembodied” form of PD that reduces gendered pressure.

In contrast, most male teachers expressed views like:

“Gender doesn’t matter as long as people are serious and professional.”

— Male teacher, Laayoune, 48, married

“Some female teachers are shy in discussions, but it’s not a real obstacle.”
— Male teacher, Marrakech, 29, single

While males tended to frame collaboration as gender-neutral, female teachers emphasized the social discomfort, family constraints, and patriarchal expectations that shaped their participation in PD.

4.7. Key Themes Emergent from Data

1. Consensus on the value of PD: Both genders view PD as essential and beneficial.
2. No statistical gender difference, but perceived differences: Women feel less empowered in leadership and more constrained by familial and social expectations.
3. Collaboration is context-dependent: While generally positive, mixed-gender collaboration is more affected by socio-cultural factors than by institutional barriers.
4. Technology levels the field: Digital platforms were seen as more equitable and flexible, especially by female participants.

5. Discussion

This study set out to examine the influence of gender on Moroccan EFL teachers’ attitudes toward professional development. Using both statistical analysis and qualitative insights, the study offers a layered understanding of how male and female teachers engage with PD and perceive their professional roles within the socio-cultural framework of Moroccan education.

5.1. Universal Agreement, Unequal Experience

One of the most compelling findings of this research is the **strong consensus** among all participants, male and female, that PD is necessary, valuable, and a professional obligation. These views align with global trends emphasizing teacher-led, self-directed development and lifelong learning (Fullan et al., 2006; Diaz-Maggioli, 2004).

However, while attitudes toward PD as a concept were similar across gender lines, the lived experiences of PD proved more complex. Quantitative analysis, particularly Chi-square tests, found no statistically significant differences in general PD attitudes, satisfaction levels, or perceptions of trainer support between male and female respondents. Yet, when teachers were invited to elaborate in interviews, clear gendered experiences emerged.

This dissonance supports the view that numbers alone can obscure deeper socio-cultural dynamics. It also confirms Hofer and Lembens' (2019) position that teacher attitudes are shaped not only by explicit knowledge and beliefs but also by affective experiences and the broader sociocultural context.

5.2. Understanding Gender Through Bourdieu's Habitus

Bourdieu's concept of *habitus* is particularly useful in interpreting the discrepancies between statistical equality and experiential disparity. Habitus refers to the deeply ingrained dispositions shaped by one's background, socialization, and cultural environment. It guides perceptions, actions, and decisions, often unconsciously.

In this study, **female teachers' habitus** appeared to be influenced by:

- **Cultural expectations** regarding women's mobility and interaction with male colleagues
- **Family responsibilities**, particularly in child-rearing and household management
- A general sense of **symbolic discomfort** or unease in assuming public leadership roles

These factors contributed to the tendency of many female teachers to either self-exclude from certain PD activities or to seek alternatives such as online collaboration, which offered more control and flexibility. These are classic manifestations of how symbolic structures (patriarchal norms, expectations of modesty or family-first roles) become internalized, shaping professional behavior.

On the other hand, male teachers' habitus, while equally shaped by social forces, appeared more aligned with institutional expectations of confidence, leadership, and public presence in professional spaces. As such, male teachers largely saw PD spaces as neutral or egalitarian, without acknowledging the invisible barriers female colleagues might experience.

This aligns with Bourdieu's notion of symbolic violence, the unconscious perpetuation of dominance through normalized structures. PD systems that ignore gendered realities may seem "fair" on the surface, but actually reproduce inequality by privileging participants who can meet its (unspoken) demands without additional constraints.

5.3. Collaboration and the Gender Divide

A key theme that emerged from the qualitative data was the gendered experience of professional collaboration. While survey responses generally praised collegiality, female

teachers often described a disconnect or distance in working with male colleagues. Their reluctance was not framed as ideological but practical and cultural: discomfort, fear of judgment, or familial pressure not to work too closely with male peers.

In contrast, male teachers often characterized collaboration as gender-neutral, suggesting that any discomfort was minimal or insignificant. This mismatch highlights how social norms regulate professional behavior differently by gender, and how male privilege in such environments often goes unexamined.

Interestingly, digital collaboration emerged as a gender-neutralizer. WhatsApp groups and online platforms were described as more accessible and less fraught with interpersonal discomfort. These spaces allow for disembodied engagement, where voice and content matter more than gender identity or physical presence. This insight is critical for policymakers seeking to expand inclusive PD opportunities.

5.4. Family, Leadership, and PD Participation

Family responsibilities were consistently cited by female participants as a constraint on PD engagement. This aligns with international findings that women in teaching often carry a “double burden” of professional and domestic roles (Çiğdem Hürsen, 2012; Taşdemir, 2013). Moroccan teachers expressed frustration at PD events being scheduled without regard for parenting duties or family life, particularly in rural areas.

Leadership in PD was another area where gender played a role. Female teachers reported that taking on leadership roles in PD, such as organizing workshops or moderating training groups, was culturally discouraged or felt personally uncomfortable. Even when not explicitly restricted, women sensed a lack of recognition or invitation into leadership spaces.

This reveals an invisible ceiling in PD engagement: women may attend and participate but are less likely to take on visible or authoritative roles unless the context is explicitly inclusive. This reinforces the need for intentional leadership development programs aimed at empowering women in education.

5.5. Implications for Policy and Practice

These findings suggest that Morocco’s ongoing education reform efforts, though well-intentioned, must adopt a more gender-sensitive lens when designing and delivering PD

opportunities. If professional development continues to be framed as gender-neutral in policy but gendered in practice, it risks reproducing the very inequalities it aims to dissolve.

Specific implications include:

- **Flexible scheduling** of PD activities, considering teachers with caregiving roles
- **Online and blended models** to increase accessibility and comfort, especially for female teachers
- **Mentorship programs** that pair junior female teachers with experienced female mentors
- **Explicit leadership development tracks** within PD programs targeting underrepresented groups
- **Institutional accountability** for inclusiveness in PD planning and delivery

Moreover, teacher education programs should integrate gender awareness training for supervisors, PD facilitators, and school leaders. This training should not only address equity as a policy goal but also as a lived experience requiring empathy, flexibility, and institutional support.

5.6. Reflecting on the Broader Context

This study contributes to a growing body of research that complicates the understanding of gender in educational settings. While many assume that the teaching profession, dominated numerically by women, is gender-progressive, the findings here reveal persistent subtle inequalities in authority, visibility, and decision-making power.

Moroccan society, like many others, remains shaped by traditional conceptions of gender roles. These extend into the classroom, the staff room, and PD events. As Fatima Sadiqi (2014) notes, “space” in Moroccan culture is both physical and symbolic, and women are often constrained in both. Whether it's physical mobility to attend workshops or the symbolic space of public speaking, gendered expectations still hold significant weight.

The challenge, then, is not only to reform structures but to transform professional cultures. PD must not only equip teachers with new techniques but also with new ways of seeing and supporting each other, as professionals shaped by different, yet valid, social realities.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study set out to explore whether gender influences Moroccan EFL teachers' attitudes and experiences with professional development. While the quantitative data showed no statistically significant differences in attitudes between male and female teachers, the qualitative insights revealed important experiential disparities. These findings point to a more nuanced understanding: gender may not shape what teachers think about PD, but it does affect how they experience it, especially regarding collaboration, leadership, and access.

6.1. Summary of Key Findings

- **Universal Support for PD:** Teachers across genders agreed on the essential role of PD in professional growth and educational reform.
- **Similar Attitudes, Different Realities:** Although statistical analysis showed no significant gender-based differences in satisfaction or general attitudes, interviews highlighted distinct experiences shaped by gender norms.
- **Cultural and Familial Pressures on Female Teachers:** Many women reported difficulties balancing PD participation with family responsibilities, particularly when activities required travel or conflicted with domestic duties.
- **Gendered Collaboration Dynamics:** Female teachers expressed more discomfort in mixed-gender professional settings, often preferring online or women-only collaboration spaces; nonetheless, male teachers were generally unaware of these barriers.
- **Underrepresentation in Leadership:** Women often felt excluded from or hesitant to pursue leadership roles within PD activities, citing cultural expectations, lack of support, and internalized norms.
- **Digital Spaces as Equalizers:** WhatsApp groups and online training sessions were seen as more inclusive, offering potential tools to bridge gender gaps in PD engagement.

6.2. Implications for Educational Policy

The findings underscore the need for **gender-sensitive planning** in professional development programs. Morocco's ambitious education reform agenda, as outlined in the *Strategic Vision 2015–2030*, will not reach its full potential if structural and cultural barriers continue to affect teachers' access to and experience of PD unequally.

While the national discourse on equity in education often focuses on students, this study shows that equity for educators is equally critical. Professional development should not assume neutrality but rather respond to the lived realities of its participants.

6.3. Recommendations

To ensure more inclusive and effective PD in Morocco and similar contexts, the following steps are recommended:

1. Design Flexible PD Formats

Offer blended learning models that include both in-person and online components. This increases accessibility for teachers with family responsibilities and those in remote areas.

2. Schedule with Gender Realities in Mind

Plan training sessions at times and locations that are mindful of teachers' caregiving roles, especially for women who may face more restrictions on travel or evening participation.

3. Promote Female Leadership in PD

Create mentorship and coaching programs that explicitly support women in taking on leadership roles within PD frameworks. Encourage female-led workshops, panels, and communities of practice.

4. Train PD Facilitators on Gender Equity

Incorporate gender-awareness modules into PD facilitator training so that session leaders are equipped to create inclusive and supportive environments.

5. Encourage Digital Collaboration

Expand the use of online PD platforms that allow asynchronous participation. These reduce social pressure and logistical barriers while maintaining professional networking and learning opportunities.

6. Collect Gender-Disaggregated PD Data

Track and analyze participation rates, leadership roles, and satisfaction levels by gender. Use this data to identify patterns, address inequities, and inform future PD planning.

7. Further Research

Support additional research that investigates the intersectionality of gender with other factors such as region, marital status, age, and institutional culture. Longitudinal and ethnographic studies would be particularly valuable in understanding evolving gender dynamics.

6.4. Final Thoughts

Gender may not be a visible divider in every PD statistic, but it is an invisible thread woven through every teacher's professional experience. To truly reform education, we must reform how we support the people at its heart. Recognizing and addressing gendered experiences

within PD is not about favoring one group over another; it is about equipping all teachers, regardless of gender, to grow, lead, and collaborate in ways that are professionally enriching and socially just.

Use of Generative AI

This manuscript made use of Chatgpt, free version, to assist in paraphrasing and improving the clarity of text, the analysis of qualitative data. No AI tools were used for the generation of research hypotheses or the writing of conclusions. The final manuscript was authored and reviewed by the listed authors without additional AI input.

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